

Quantum Mechanical, Statistical Mechanical and Classical Spatial Probability Distributions

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Quantum mechanical spatial probability densities may be obtained by solving the time independent Schrodinger equation. Statistical mechanical spatial densities may be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy $d(r)\ln[d(r)]$ (where $d(r)$ is the spatial density) subject to appropriate constraints. A classical spatial probability density may be obtained from $1/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the velocity at position x obtained from kinetic energy + potential energy $(x) = \text{total energy}$. [1]. Recently, there have been attempts to link these various spatial probability densities. For example for the ground state wavefunction of a harmonic oscillator, the Schrodinger equation can be obtained from varying Shannon's entropy with constraints because $V(x) W^*(x) W(x)$ (where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction) can be written in the form of Shannon's entropy times a constant [3]. Furthermore, Casal et al [4] have maximized Tsallis' entropy to obtain good approximations to the ground state wavefunctions of oscillators and Coulomb potentials. In [1], the classical density $1/v(x)$ has been calculated using energy levels from quantum mechanics, namely $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$. This density has in turn been used to calculate entropy and compared with results from wavefunctions of the Schrodinger equation with good results even for low n values even though for $n=0$, the wavefunction $W(x) = 1/C \exp(-ax^2)$ and $1/v(x)$ are not at all similar. The purpose of this note, is to attempt to examine the relationship between these different spatial densities.

Classical Spatial Density

In [1], the authors consider a classical harmonic oscillator and assign a position probability distribution based on the amount of time spent in each region of space. In particular, they use $dx = v dt$ and set dt equal to the probability at x or $P(x) = dx/v$. They then use $v = \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))}$ where $V(x) = .5k x^2$.

$$\text{Thus: } P(x) = dx / \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))} \quad (1)$$

The authors of [1] then calculate Shannon's entropy using values for E from quantum mechanics $(n + .5) \hbar \omega$, where ω is the frequency. This classical set of values of Shannon's entropy is compared with quantum mechanical wave function results: $\int W(x) \ln(W(x)) dx$ where $W(x)$, the wavefunction is equal to $\exp(-ax^2) H_n(x)$ where $H_n(x)$ is a Hermite polynomial. The authors obtain close agreement between the two even down to $n=0$ although the closest agreement is for $n > 10$.

It may be good to consider the classical position density of [1] in more detail (1). If one considers the time independent single particle Schrodinger equation, then one has:

$$1 / \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))} = (W(x)W(x)) / \{W(x) \hbar^2 \text{del}^2 W(x)\}$$

Thus, the classical position probability density is not the same as that of the quantum mechanical result $W^*(x)W(x)$. For the harmonic oscillator, for high n , however, the envelope of $W^*(x)W(x)$ approaches the classical density. What is interesting, however, is that the wavefunction $W(x)$ contains information about classical motion, as one can write:

$$(2m(E-V(x)) W^*(x)W(x)) = \{W^*(x) \hbar^2 \text{del}^2 W(x) \}$$

The wavefunction is such that Laplacian retrieves the classical kinetic energy at each point x multiplied by the quantum mechanical spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ (whose envelope eventually matches $1/v(x)$ for high energy levels.) This classical kinetic energy, however, is $E-V(x)$, so one may argue that one is obtaining information about the potential, especially in the case of the ground state. (If one writes $W(x)$ as a Fourier series the term with the Laplacian shows kinetic energies of various plane waves, but a clear interpretation is needed. For the case of the Gaussian ground state, the Fourier transform is also a Gaussian in p which is identical to statistical mechanical results.) It should be noted that the statistical mechanical spatial density $\exp(-aV(x)/T)$ contains information about the classical potential $V(x)$, but that there is no collective flow of particles, rather there is a stationary equilibrium picture.

2x2 Matrix Model

In [6], a 2x2 matrix model was found to be contained in Einstein's 1905 equation $E^2=p^2+m^2$. This model, similar to the Dirac equation, predicts zitterbewegung, but also yields an expectation value of the velocity matrix equal to v , the particle velocity. Thus, in the model, the particle is undergoing complicated zitterbewegung motion in a periodic fashion (with the particle moving back and forth), but on average has a position and a velocity corresponding to classical mechanics. There also appears to be a wavelength associated with this zitterbewegung motion, which depends on the velocity v . It was suggested by the author of [6] that zitterbewegung motion in the 2x2 matrix model may be replaced with periodic functions $\exp(iEt)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$ in an attempt to model zitterbewegung. It was then suggested that the Schrodinger equation may apply as a conservation of energy equation with a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum a_j \exp(-i k_j x)$ where different motions of the 2x2 particle can interfere. Given that a particle can be found in a region of space at least the size of the wavelength in the 2x2 model (i.e. it is undergoing zitterbewegung), interactions it seems are not local. In [2], the authors use zitterbewegung to argue that this nonlocality of interactions allow a particle to interfere or sense two slits in a two slit interference experiment, even though it passes through one.

Thus, it seems that if a 2x2 matrix model particle is in a potential and there is scattering to different velocity values (due to the potential), zitterbewegung of the two different velocities should interfere, at least for a certain amount of time during which the interaction occurs. The uncertainty of position appears to be real and one does not know if a particle still has a velocity v or has interacted and has a different velocity. This may also apply to a particle in a box which reflects from the infinite potential at the walls. One cannot be certain whether the particle is going forwards or backwards due to the zitterbewegung/wavelength even though on average it

behaves with the motion $x=vt$, the actual motion is very different at least in regions with lengths comparable to the wavelength. It is as if there is a classical average motion governed by conservation of energy (which appears in the time independent Schrodinger equation) as well zitterbewegung motion going backwards and forwards which can interfere with zitterbewegung motion resulting from nonlocal interactions with the potential. The classical average motion, however, is maintained as:

$$W^*(x) \hbar^2/2m \text{del}^2 W(x) = (E-V(x))W^*(x)W(x) = .5m v(x)^2 W^*(x)W(x)$$

The last term shows how the classical kinetic energy is maintained at each point in space,, but is multiplied by the quantum mechanical density created by zitterbewegung and interference between different zitterbewegung motions. For high energy levels, $W^*(x)W(x)$ has an envelope which is similar to $1/v(x)$ and one may expect collective velocity but it is not clear that this interpretation necessarily holds for the ground state.

It should be noted that many people have developed derivations of the Schrodinger equation using stochastic mechanics with an average motion and a Gaussian random motion. Others have proposed replacing the Gaussian random motion with zitterbewegung. [8]

Comparison with Statistical Mechanics

It is interesting to consider probability densities from statistical mechanics. In the Boltzmann transport equation approach, conservation of kinetic energy and momentum is used and a probability result of $\exp(-E/T)$ is obtained where $E=\text{Kinetic energy} + V(x)$, where $V(x)$ is the potential energy. Thus, Newtonian mechanics is part of the formalism, but the probability result is in keeping with Newtonian pressure balancing. Unlike the classical result, the reaction to the force is not an acceleration of a particle, but a shifting of spatial density to counteract the force. This results in no collective motion,unlike the classical Newtonian case. For example, consider (as in statistical mechanics textbooks) a small box at position x . Then, using the ideal gas law, one finds that

$$\begin{aligned} T \text{ density}(x-dx/2) - T \text{ density}(x+dx/2) &= T \exp[-V(x-dx/2)/T] - T \exp[-V(x+dx/2)/T] \\ &= -dV/dx \\ &= \text{force} \end{aligned}$$

If one tries to obtain the spatial density by maximizing Shannon's entropy one can use the constraint: $\int d(x) V(x) dx = \text{a constant}$. This statistical mechanical position density is not equal to (1) as (1) predicts high probability densities for low velocities, i.e. high potential positions, while statistical mechanics predicts low densities for high potential positions.

A question arises as to why this maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint guarantees pressure balance in the case in which the ideal gas law applies i.e.

pressure=density(x)T. Shannon's entropy increases when there is more uncertainty. If one maximizes Shannon's entropy and there is no pressure balance then there could be collective motion of particles. This would mean one would know the collective velocity of a large number of particles which in turn would decrease the value of Shannon's entropy. By having no collective flows i.e. pressure balance, one increases Shannon's entropy. This is interesting because in quantum mechanics, $\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 W(x)$ is equal to the classical kinetic energy at the point $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2$ times $W^*(x)W(x)$. One might argue that this implies collective flow especially at high energy levels where the envelope of $W^*(x)W(x)$ approximates $1/v(x)$. By the above argument, this would mean that Shannon's entropy is not maximized. For the ground state, however, one can note that $\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 W(x)$ is equal to $(E-V(x))W(x)$. If one writes $V(x)W(x)$ as $b W(x) \ln(W^*(x)W(x))$ then the Schrodinger equation for the ground state of the oscillator can be written as:

$$b W(x) \ln(W^*(x)W(x)) - V(x)W(x)=0$$

This is exactly the result of statistical mechanics with density replaced by $W^*(x)W(x)$ and variation performed on $W^*(x)$ (which is done traditionally in the literature). [9] This might imply that in some cases (the ground state of the harmonic oscillator) there is no clear collective motion.

In addition, as mentioned the Fourier transform of a Gaussian is a Gaussian in p which is identical to statistical mechanics where there is no collective motion.

Is there any link between the classical spatial density $1/v(x)$ and statistical mechanics? We attempt to present a hand-waving argument. Imagine a potential $V(r)$ in two dimensions with $V(r)=0$ at $r=0$ (such as the oscillator potential) and imagine many different particles starting out with different speeds distributed according to the Boltzmann distribution. Each particle is subject to a classical trajectory governed by $KE + V(r) = \text{Energy}$, but because some particles have small velocities they will reach 0 velocity before others. Consider:

$$\int \exp(-p^2/2mT) \frac{1}{\sqrt{p^2/2m - V(r)}} P dp \quad (6.28)$$

One can choose a point r and integrate by changing variables to:

$z=p^2/2m - V(r)$. Then, one has an integral with a factor of $\exp(-V(r)/T)$ sitting outside, which is the statistical density as z can extend from 0 to infinity.

Quantum Mechanical Density

At first, it may seem that the probabilistic theory contained in quantum mechanics for a single particle has nothing to do with classical statistical mechanics which applies for a temperature. If one looks at pure Gaussian states (wavefunction) $W(x)=\exp(-.5dx^2)$ (where d is a constant) which is the ground state of the harmonic oscillator then $W(x) V(x) W(x)$ takes on the form of Shannon's entropy, that is: $\text{constant } W(x)^*W(x) \ln [W^*(x)W(x)]$. Thus, the Schrodinger equation, multiplied by $W(x)$, the wavefunction looks like a function of Shannon's entropy with a

set of constraints related to the potential (although the x^2 term has a different coefficient). There is also the unusual constraint of $W^*(x) \hbar^2/2m \text{del}^2 W(x)$. Thus, for this specific case, the Schrodinger equation appears to be related to a variational problem using Shannon's entropy and varying with respect to W^* . As a result, it is not surprising that the quantum mechanical ground state $\exp(-m\omega x^2/2\hbar)$ where ω is the oscillator angular frequency appears to be very similar to the square root of the density from statistical mechanics. Both are obtained from maximizing Shannon's entropy with respect to similar constraints as the $W^*(x) \text{del}^2 W(x) \hbar^2/2m$ term from QM is equivalent in the ground state case to $(E-V(x)) W^*(x)W(x)$ which is the same constraint used in statistical mechanics. For the case of the ground state, $V(x)W^*(x)W(x)$ is not just Shannon's entropy, but is also part of a variance calculation of $W^*(x)W(x)$ as $\text{variance}^2 = \text{expectation}(x^2) - [\text{expectation}(x)]^2$.

If one has a wavefunction $W(x)$ similar to a statistical mechanical result $\exp(-aV(x))$ then one is lead to the equation:

$$-\hbar^2/2m [d^2V/dx^2 - a\{dV/dx\}^2] = E-V \quad \text{where } V \text{ is the potential.}$$

$V=x^2$ is a possible solution.

For higher n values the wavefunction is $\exp(-ax^2) H_n(x)$ where H_n is a Hermite polynomial. In such a case, the Shannon's entropy does not appear naturally in the Schrodinger equation. It seems that as one increases n , the overall energy increases and the average classical motion becomes more pronounced although the oscillating peaks of quantum mechanics can still be seen.[1]

Thus, for the ground state oscillator wavefunction there appears to be a connection between quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics. Is there also a connection with classical mechanics? The time independent Schrodinger equation may be written as:

$$\hbar^2/2m \text{del}^2 W(x) = [E-V(x)] W^*(x) W(x) \quad (\text{for potentials which are functions of } x)$$

Now $(E-V(x)) = m/2 v(x)^2$ which is the classical kinetic energy. Thus, classical values are part of the Schrodinger equation, however, $W^*(x)W(x)$ does not need to be similar to $1/v(x)$, the classical spatial density. In the section on the 2x2 matrix model, an attempt at partially explaining this has been given. For the case of the harmonic oscillator, however, it has been shown that the envelope of $W^*(x)W(x)$ approaches $1/v(x)$ so there is a connection between classical spatial densities and quantum mechanical motion.[7]

Conclusion

In conclusion, it appears that quantum mechanical spatial density may be related to classical densities $1/v(x)$ and statistical mechanical densities at least in some cases. (There is also the feature of peaks and troughs due to deBroglie wavelengths in the quantum case.) For low

energies, for example the ground state, it may be possible to link quantum mechanics to the maximization of Shannon's entropy (or other entropy expressions) subject to constraints at least in the case of a Gaussian wavefunction. Actually, the authors of [4] have gone further and maximize Tsallis' entropy for q-Gaussian related problems and apply this to harmonic oscillators and the Coulomb potential. Nevertheless, the Schrodinger equation also enforces classical conservation of energy and there seems to be an average classical kinetic energy at each point multiplied by a quantum mechanical density (due perhaps to zitterbewegung and the interference of different zitterbewegung due to nonlocal collisions with the potential.)

$$W^*(x) \hbar^2/2m \text{del}^2 W(x) = (E-V(x))W^*(x)W(x) = .5m v(x)^2 W^*(x)W(x)$$

According to the correspondence principle, as the energy level increases, the envelope of $W^*(x)W(x)$ apparently approaches the classical result of $1/v(x)$. [7]

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